

Speculation on E and p As Temporal and Spatial Entropies Linked to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 12, 2026

In previous notes, we have argued that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ (the spatial free particle probability) from the maximization of $P1(x) \ln(P1(x)) + i \int px P1(x)$, and a similar expression for $P2(t)$. This yields $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If one integrates $\int_{px=0}^{2\pi\hbar/p} px \exp(ipx) dx$ from $px=0$ to $2\pi\hbar/p$, one obtains $i 2\pi\hbar/p$ as a spatial entropy and $i^2 2\pi\hbar/E$ as a temporal one associated with the complex probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If one considers classical motion of a free particle in space, then there is no uncertainty in time or space and so one might create a classical level entropy of: $-E dt + p dx$, where $dt=\hbar/E$ and $dx=\hbar/p$. This yields $-Edt+pdx=0$ and one might equate this with a classical entropy dS as done in (1). This overall classical entropy is different from the spatial and temporal wave entropies dx and dt .

If one does not wish to work at the classical level, one might try to use the \hbar/p , \hbar/E entropies in a problem requiring $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, such as 1-D reflection-refraction at an n_1-n_2 index of refraction junction ($x=0$). In such a case, it seems that one does not use entropies, but rather their reciprocals which indicate the amount of resolution information present, i.e. $L/dx = Lp/\hbar$. As a result, conservation of E and p may be reformulated in terms of a balance of resolution information which is the reciprocal of dx , i.e. p (in the spatial case). For example, a particle at rest may break into two pieces with p and -p. The resolution is proportional to p initial =0 and after one has p and -p (i.e. conservation) of momentum which may be argued to be equivalent to conservation of resolution information.

Using the notion of a balance of the reciprocal of entropy (i.e. p which is linked to conservation of momentum), one might interpret:

$A_p - B_p = C p^2$ where $p^2=n^2 p$ in terms of resolution and not momentum conservation, i.e.

$A-B = C p^2/p$ where $p^2/p = n^2$ is the greater relative resolution of the p^2 photon.

The idea of both a wave entropy (both temporal \hbar/E and \hbar/p) and its reciprocal resolution information seem to arise as well an overall classical entropy $-Edt+pdx = 0$ if $dt=\hbar/E$ and $\hbar/hp = 0$.

$dt=\hbar/E$ and $dx= \hbar/p$

We have argued in previous notes that one may obtain:

$dt=\hbar/E$ and $dx=\hbar/p$ ((1)) as independent dx and dt fluctuation from the Lorentz invariant.

One may show that $-Et+px$ is equivalent to the classical relativistic or nonrelativistic action Lt if

$Lt=.5m_0v^2 t$ (nonrelativistic) or $Lt = -m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} t$ (relativistic) and $x/t=v$ ((2))

The reason that one recasts Lt as $-Et+px$ is to use relativistic variables. The notion of an action remaining unchanged under a fluctuation $\delta x(t)$, i.e. at t one considers x_1 instead to $x=vt$, leads to:

$$0 = -E \delta t + p \delta x = 0 \text{ which has a solution of } ((1)).$$

In (1), however, the notion of an overall entropy is introduced such that:

$$dS = 0 = -E \delta t + p \delta x \quad ((3))$$

Given that one really has a probabilistic scenario (free particle quantum mechanics) associated with ((1)), i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ = probability which ensures ((1)) and also spatial and temporal invariance by the unit modulus (less information than $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$), then one might consider the notion of an overall entropy.

Spatial and Temporal Entropies

We have argued in previous notes that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ separately through maximization of entropy subject to an appropriate constraint. We consider $\exp(ipx)$ because $\exp(-iEt)$ follows in an analogous manner.

$$\text{Maximize } -P_1(x) \ln(P_1(x)) + ipx P_1(x) \rightarrow \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

In such a case, spatial entropy should be:

$$2\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{p} \exp(ipx) p dx \quad ((5))$$

Using $\int x \sin x dx = -x \cos(x) + \sin(x)$ and a similar expression for $\int x \cos(x) dx$.

((5)), however, is proportional to δx from ((1)).

One might consider δt as being temporal entropy ((6)).

We note that δx and δt are unusual entropies linked with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is not the classical $W^*(x)W(x)$ probability. As a result, they must be handled with care. We note at first that it is the reciprocal of δx , δt (or the wave entropies) which are the conserved quantities. As a result, the second law of thermodynamics does not seem to apply to these entropies because for:

$$p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4 \quad 1/p_1 + 1/p_2 \neq 1/p_3 + 1/p_4 \text{ in general } ((7))$$

Given that the reaction may go in either direction, one can have an increase in entropy in one case followed by a decrease. In equilibrium, however, there is a time reversal balance and so even this total entropy remains constant on average in a gas system.

We note that the reciprocals of Δx and Δt are:

E and p ((8))

E and p are conserved quantities and so may be used in problems. If, however, one wishes to have a strictly statistical viewpoint, one might argue that E and p are associated with temporal and spatial resolutions. This is in fact a physical description and so we argue it should be pursued.

If one considers 1-D reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction (at $x=0$), then one has the two equations:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{where } p_2 = n_2 \cdot p \quad ((9a)) \text{ and}$$

$$A \exp(ipx) - pB \exp(-ipx) = Cp_2 \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((9b))$$

The second equation may be considered as a kind of conservation of momentum, but we suggest that one may think in terms of a balance of information resolution. First, we argue that p and $-p$ represent resolution information which cancels. Thus:

$$A - B = C \frac{p_2}{p} = C n_2 \quad ((10))$$

$A - B$ is the wave resolution information of the incident (A) and reflected (B) photons, while the refracted photon (weight C) has n_2 times the resolution information as A, B . ((10)) then represents a balance of resolution information (as well as momentum balance) we argue. We suggest that one might be able to look at this from both points of view.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued in previous notes that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ (free particle quantum probabilities) through maximization of entropy: $-P_1(x) \ln(P_1(x)) + ipx P_1(x)$. If this is the case, then one has a spatial entropy: $-\int dx (0, 2\pi\hbar/p) p x \exp(ipx) i dx = 2\pi\hbar^2/p$ and $2\pi\hbar^2/E$ for time, or $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ as entropies. We note that like in (1), $-E\Delta t + p\Delta x$ might equal a classical dS such that both are 0. Δt and Δx would then be fluctuations which leave the classical action $-Et + px$ (if $v=x/t$) unchanged as well $dS=0$. dS here is an overall classical type entropy, whereas we suggest that Δx and Δt are spatial and temporal wave entropies.

We argue that in practical problems, one may use the reciprocal of the spatial and temporal entropies p and E (which are conserved) quantities as representing spatial and time resolutions. In such a case, conservation of E or p might be also interpreted as a conservation of spatial or temporal resolution. For example, in 1D reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction at $x=0$, one has $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x)$ $p_2 = n_2 \cdot p$ and $A p \exp(ipx) - pB \exp(-ipx) = Cp_2 \exp(ip_2x)$. The second equation is a balance of momentum, but one may

write $C \frac{p^2}{p} = C \cdot n^2$ showing that one has a balance of spatial resolution if p and $-p$ cancel such a resolution (i.e. A-B) for the incident and reflected weights.

References

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